

PAPER ID: IJPS/240208128

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

ISSN: 0975-4725

Certificate of Publication

This is to certify that

Mayuri Mhatre, Corresponding Author

Department of Pharmaceutics, Shri D.D. Vispute College of Pharmacy and Research Centre, New Panvel

Published a paper entitled

"Microemulsion-Based Topical Therapies: Exploring New Potential"

Volume 2 – Issue 8 - 2024

ijpsjournal.com

Editor-In-Chief

PAPER ID: IJPS/240208128

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

ISSN: 0975-4725

Certificate of Publication

This is to certify that

Gangotri Yadav, Co-Author

Department of Pharmaceutics, Shri D.D. Vispute College of Pharmacy and Research Centre, New Panvel

Published a paper entitled

"Microemulsion-Based Topical Therapies: Exploring New Potential"

Volume 2 – Issue 8 - 2024

ijpsjournal.com

Editor-In-Chief

PAPER ID: IJPS/240208128

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

ISSN: 0975-4725

Certificate of Publication

This is to certify that

Ashish Jain, Co-Author

Department of Pharmaceutics, Shri D.D. Vispute College of Pharmacy and Research Centre, New Panvel

Published a paper entitled

"Microemulsion-Based Topical Therapies: Exploring New Potential"

Volume 2 – Issue 8 - 2024

ijpsjournal.com

Editor-In-Chief

